

Fuqiang Gao

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Research Interests

My researches focus on different aspects of rock mechanics and rock engineering design in both surface and underground situations. In particular, I have been heavily involved in the utilization of advanced numerical modeling techniques in conjunction with discontinuity mapping to examine and better understand complex failure processes of intact rock at laboratory scale to rock mass at field scale. Other research topics include applications of synthetic rock mass modeling and discrete fracture network modeling, the integration of geological, geotechnical and geophysical field investigations, in situ testing and monitoring, physical modeling and laboratory testing.

Research Contributions

- Development of a Trigon modeling approach in UDEC and 3DEC

The incorporation of brittle fracture in distinct element models is increasingly recognized to be essential in realistic modeling of failure and post failure in rock engineering. The proposed Trigon modification to existing Voronoi methods in 2D and particularly in 3D represent an important addition to the numerical modeling toolbox and offer significant potential improvements in our ability to simulate brittle fracture in rock engineering. The UDEC Trigon has been incorporated in the latest UDEC 6.0 version.

- Development of a Grain-bonded model in UDEC Grain-scale

Microstructure controls the micromechanical behavior and hence the complex macroscopic response of intact rock. A distinct element grain-based method (GBM) was developed to simulate the microstructure of low-porosity sandstone, allowing realistic fracturing of polygonal grains. The proposed numerical approach allows the independent assignment of specific properties to both the grains and grain boundaries, and provides a complete tracking of the formation of intra-granular cracks cutting through the grains and trans-granular cracks forming along grain boundaries.

Experience

06/2014- Current **Mining Branch, State Key Laboratory of Coal Mining and Clear Utilization, China Coal Research Institute** — Beijing

Vice Dean

Leading state key projects of characterization of fracture propagation in roof strata with extraction of longwall coal panels, assessment methods for roof collapse hazards, and company projects of development of in situ stress data base of Chinese coalfields and Coal Measures classification. Using the combination of numerical modeling, laboratory tests and physical modeling to study rock failure mechanisms with emphasis on post-peak behavior and residual strength, rock

bust and coal bump mechanics, rock mass behavior at tunnel-scale from the onset of acoustic emissions through to yield, and collapse.

10/2012-06/2014 **Golder Associates — Burnaby, BC**
Rock Mechanics Specialist

Used sophisticated numerical methods along with empirical and analytical techniques to conduct rock mechanics analyses of underground and open pit mines, specializing in rock mass characterization, sand production analysis, inter-ramp and overall slope stability analysis, and interaction with underground mining.

07/2006-04/2009 **China Coal Research Institute — Beijing**
Mining Engineer

Experience with underground room-and-pillar and longwall operations includes sequencing and dimensioning of excavations and pillars, stability analysis and ground support design for entries and cross sections, and the assessment of hazards related to rock burst, coal bump, roof collapse, and ground subsidence.

Education

2003 **China University of Mining and Technology — Xuzhou, Jiangsu, China**
Bachelor of Science: Mining Engineering

2006 **China University of Mining and Technology — Xuzhou, Jiangsu, China**
Master of Science: Mining Engineering

2013 **Simon Fraser University — Burnaby, BC, Canada**
Ph.D.: Geomechanics

Publications (Peer Reviewed Journals)

- Gao F*, Kang H (2016) Experimental study on the residual strength of coal under low confinement. *Rock Mech Rock Eng.* On line. doi: 10.1007/s00603-016-1120-z
- Gao F*, Stead D, Elmo D (2016) Numerical simulation of microstructure of brittle rock using a grain-breakable distinct element grain-based model. *Comput Geotech* 78:203–217. doi: 10.1016/j.compgeo.2016.05.019
- Gao F*, Kang H, Wu Y (2016) Experimental and numerical study on the effect of calcite on the mechanical behaviour of coal. *Int J Coal Geol* 158: 119–128. doi: 10.1016/j.coal.2016.03.008
- Gao F*, Kang HP (2016) Effects of pre-existing discontinuities on the residual strength of rock mass – Insight from a discrete element method simulation. *J Struct Geol* 85:40–50. doi: 10.1016/j.jsg.2016.02.010
- Kang H*, Lv H, Zhang X, Gao F, et al (2015) Evaluation of the Ground Response of a Pre-driven Longwall Recovery Room Supported by Concrete Cribs. *Rock Mech Rock Eng* 1–16. doi: 10.1007/s00603-015-0782-2
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characteristics using an innovative UDEC Trigon approach. *Comput Geotech* 55:448–460. doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2013.09.020

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- Gao F*, Stead D, Kang H, Wu Y (2014) Discrete element modelling of deformation and damage of a roadway driven along an unstable goaf — A case study. *Int J Coal Geol* 127:100–110. doi: 10.1016/j.coal.2014.02.010
- Gao F*, Stead D (2013) Discrete element modelling of cutter roof failure in coal mine roadways. *Int J Coal Geol* 116–117:158–171. doi: 10.1016/j.coal.2013.07.020
- Kang H*, Wu Y, Gao F, et al (2013) Fracture characteristics in rock bolts in underground coal mine roadways. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 62:105–112. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrmms.2013.04.006
- Coggan J*, Gao F, Stead D, Elmo D (2012) Numerical modelling of the effects of weak immediate roof lithology on coal mine roadway stability. *Int J Coal Geol* 90–91:100–109. doi: 10.1016/j.coal.2011.11.003
- Kang H*, Zhang X, Si L, Gao F, et al (2010) In-situ stress measurements and stress distribution characteristics in underground coal mines in China. *Eng Geol* 116:333–345. doi: 10.1016/j.enggeo.2010.09.015

References

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